

ABOUT GLOBAL WARMING.

Atabayeva Zarina.

Student of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages.

Abstract: *In this article, I will explain that global warming has an influence nature, worldwild, forests, plants, ocean, seas, lakes, and humanity.*

Key words: *climate change, degree, dry, greenhouse, temperature.*

Weather refers to atmospheric conditions that occur locally over short periods of time from minutes to hours or days. Familiar examples include rain, snow, clouds, winds, floods or thunderstorms. Climate, on the other hand, refers to the long-term regional or even global average of temperature, humidity and rainfall patterns over seasons, years or decades. Global warming will change things between the poles, too. Many already-dry areas are expected to get even drier as the world warms.

Global warming is the long-term heating of Earth's climate system observed since the pre-industrial period due to human activities, primarily fossil fuel burning, which increases heat-trapping greenhouse gas levels in Earth's atmosphere. The term is frequently used interchangeably with the term climate change, though the latter refers to both human and naturally produced warming and the effects it has on our planet. It is most commonly measured as the average increase in Earth's global surface temperature.

Climate change is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth's local, regional and global climates. These changes have a broad range of observed effects that are synonymous with the term. Changes observed in Earth's climate since the early 20th century are primarily driven by human activities, particularly fossil fuel burning, which increases heat-trapping greenhouse gas levels in Earth's atmosphere, raising Earth's average surface temperature. These human-produced temperature increases are commonly referred to as global warming. Natural processes can also contribute to climate change, including internal variability and external forcings.

Scientists use observations from the ground, air and space, along with theoretical models, to monitor and study past, present and future climate change. Climate data records provide evidence of climate change key indicators, such as global land and ocean temperature increases; rising sea levels; ice loss at Earth’s poles and in mountain glaciers; frequency and severity changes in extreme weather such as hurricanes, heatwaves, wildfires, droughts, floods and precipitation; Global warming is the rise in average temperatures across the globe, which has been ongoing at least since record keeping began in 1880.

Modern global warming is caused by humans. The burning of fossil fuels has released greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, which trap warmth from the sun and drive up surface and air temperatures. Global warming is a synonym for climate change, though “climate change”.

Scientists already have documented these impacts of climate change:

Ice is melting worldwide, especially at the Earth’s poles. This includes mountain glaciers, ice sheets covering West Antarctica and Greenland, and Arctic sea ice. Rising temperatures are affecting wildlife and their habitats. As temperatures change, many species are on the move. Some butterflies, foxes, and alpine plants have migrated farther north or to higher, cooler areas.

Plants and trees play an important role in regulating the climate because they absorb carbon dioxide from the air and release oxygen back into it. Forests and bushland act as carbon sinks and are a valuable means of keeping global warming.

Global warming will have a significant influence on the development, growth, and yield of all plants and particularly of seed-producing food crops. However, the effects of global warming will vary depending upon climatic conditions at various locations on earth. Oceans and seas are mostly affected by the process of change caused by global warming, as they constitute a large portion of our planet and have rich biodiversity. A temperature increase of only a few degrees does not only cause for increase in the temperature of large water masses such as oceans, seas, lakes, and ponds but also causes hydrological events that caused a change in the physical and chemical characteristics of water. Water temperature is the most important

environmental parameter that affects the life cycle, physiology, and behaviors of aquatic living beings.

Conclusion.

Since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution, humans have been rapidly changing the balance of gases in the atmosphere. Burning fossil fuels like coal and oil releases water vapor, carbon dioxide, methane, ozone and nitrous oxide, which are considered the primary greenhouse gases. Carbon dioxide is the most common greenhouse gas.

References:

- 1.Livescience.com.
- 2.<https://www.biologicaldiversity.org/organisation>.
- 3.<https://www.gale.com>.